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RISK FACTORS FOR ABNORMAL UTERINE BLEEDING IN WOMEN OF REPRODUCTIVE AGE

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Introduction. Uterine bleeding is the most common indication for emergency hospitalization in gynecology, and despite the achievements of modern medicine, even in developed countries the frequency of surgical interventions for uterine bleeding remains high. Uterine bleeding causes physical, emotional, social and material discomfort to patients, reduces reproductive potential. The high frequency of uterine bleeding in women of reproductive age entails not only medical but also economic consequences. Women with menstrual irregularities more often complain of anxiety, depression, insomnia, excessive sleepiness and pain syndrome. In this regard, determining the relationship between abnormal uterine bleeding in women and quality of life is an urgent problem in modern medicine.

Aim: Identification of risk factors for abnormal uterine bleeding in women of reproductive age.

Materials and methods. The study included 22 women of reproductive age with AUB. A control group consisted of 20 clinically healthy women. Anamnestic, medical-social, and clinical indicators of the women were collected and subjected to comparative analysis.

Results. Analysis of somatic pathology in women with AUB revealed the most common conditions to be anemia (48,5%), acute respiratory infections (31,3%), cardiovascular diseases (31,3%), chronic tonsillitis (26,9%), and chronic gastritis (20,9%). Evaluation of menstrual function in women with AUB compared to healthy women showed prolonged (more than 8 days, $\chi^2=88,1$, $p=0,00001$) and heavy menstrual bleeding ($\chi^2=72,82$, $p=0,00001$).

In the main group, 72,5% of women reported stressful situations in their family life, whereas women in the control group reported no such experiences ($\chi^2=13,9$, $p=0,0028$). We highlighted that women with AUB were 4.1 times more likely to experience stressful situations in their family life (85,2%; $\chi^2=32,0$, $p=0,00001$).

To predict the recurrence of AUB in women, we employed binary logistic regression. Stepwise regression analysis identified only 4 indicators as significant predictors of AUB: heavy menstrual bleeding (more than 80 ml), chronic stress in family and life, chronic tonsillitis, and frequent acute respiratory infections. Constant and logistic regression coefficients were calculated for each. The predictive ability of the model was evaluated based on the area under the ROC curve (AUC). Statistical parameters of the ROC curve indicated an area under the curve of 0,954 (95% CI: 0,922–0,986), with a standard error of 0,016 ($p<0,001$), demonstrating the model's excellent predictive capability. A cut-off value of 0,30 (30%) not only improved the accuracy of correct predictions for AUB recurrence but also enhanced the overall informativeness of the regression model. Thus, the high informativeness, good predictive quality, and ease of application of the recommended model allow its use in clinical practice to assess the risk of AUB recurrence in women.

Conclusions. Women with AUB were diagnosed with somatic pathologies 3-5 times more frequently than healthy women (anemia – 48,5%, cardiovascular diseases – 31,3%, chronic gastritis – 20,9%, acute respiratory infections – 31,3%). Additionally, chronic stress in family (67,9%) and workplace (76,9%) environments was observed, leading to changes in reproductive system function. Heavy menstrual bleeding (more than 80 ml, $p=0,001$), chronic family stress ($p=0,0028$), chronic tonsillitis ($p<0,001$), and frequent acute respiratory infections ($p<0,001$) should be considered as prognostic risk factors for the occurrence and recurrence of AUB.

COMPARATIVE EVALUATION OF MATERNAL MICRONUTRIENT SUPPLEMENTATION AND NEONATAL OUTCOMES IN URBAN AND RURAL TERTIARY HOSPITALS OF INDIA AND UZBEKISTAN

Virmani S., Sattarova K. A.

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Introduction: Micronutrient supplementation during pregnancy is critical for optimal fetal growth and maternal health. However, disparities in supplement adherence and clinical outcomes persist between urban and rural healthcare settings. India and Uzbekistan provide free antenatal care services, but the impact of these services on maternal and neonatal outcomes remains inconsistent across regions.

Aim: To compare maternal micronutrient supplementation adherence and related neonatal outcomes between urban and rural tertiary care hospitals in India and Uzbekistan.

Materials and Methods: A prospective observational study was conducted among 200 pregnant women (50 each from Delhi, Bihar, Tashkent, and Tashkent Region) from January to December 2024. Women enrolled at ≤ 20 weeks gestation were followed until 6 months postpartum. Clinical data collected included IFA, calcium, vitamin D adherence, maternal haemoglobin levels, antenatal visit frequency, and neonatal outcomes such as birth weight, Apgar scores, gestational age, and Denver Developmental Screening Test (DDST) at 6 months. Data analysis was performed using SPSS v25.0 with $p<0.05$ considered statistically significant.

Results: IFA adherence was highest in Delhi (90%) and Tashkent (84%), while Bihar and Tashkent Region showed lower rates (66% and 60%, respectively; $p=0.001$). Anaemia prevalence ($Hb<10g/dL$) was significantly higher in Bihar (40%) and Tashkent Region (38%) compared to Delhi (18%) and Tashkent (22%; $p=0.003$). Mean birth weights: Delhi – 3.1kg, Bihar – 2.55kg, Tashkent – 3.05kg, Tashkent Region – 2.6kg ($p<0.001$). Low birth weight ($<2.5kg$) rates: Bihar – 30%, Tashkent Region – 28%, vs. Delhi – 8%, Tashkent – 10% ($p=0.002$). Preterm birth rates:

Bihar – 18%, Tashkent Region – 16%, vs. Delhi – 6%, Tashkent – 8% ($p=0.04$). Delayed DDST milestones at 6 months were more prevalent in Bihar (20%) and Tashkent Region (18%) than in Delhi (6%) and Tashkent (8%) ($p=0.01$). Placental histopathology in LBW/preterm births showed increased villous infarction, syncytial knotting, and calcification in rural populations.

Conclusions: Urban centres demonstrated better maternal nutritional compliance and improved neonatal outcomes. Rural settings showed higher anaemia rates and poorer developmental indices despite similar policy frameworks. Strengthening antenatal education, ensuring consistent supplement availability, and region-specific intervention strategies are critical to improving maternal and neonatal health in underserved populations.

IMPACT OF MATERNAL VITAMIN D STATUS ON PERINATAL OUTCOMES

Wahi N.

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Introduction: Vitamin D is an essential nutrient that plays a significant role in calcium metabolism, immune function, and fetal development. During pregnancy, adequate vitamin D levels are crucial for proper placental function, fetal growth, and maternal health. However, vitamin D deficiency remains highly prevalent among pregnant women worldwide, particularly in Asian countries, where up to 80% of pregnant women have insufficient levels. Studies suggest that low maternal vitamin D levels may contribute to various adverse perinatal outcomes, including preeclampsia, preterm birth, intrauterine growth restriction (IUGR), and low birth weight. Despite growing evidence, routine vitamin D screening and supplementation remain inconsistent in many clinical settings.

Aim: This study aims to assess whether pregnant women with low vitamin D levels have a higher risk of complications compared to those with normal levels.

Materials and methods: A clinical study involving 40 pregnant women was conducted at Maternity Complex No. 9 in Tashkent, Uzbekistan. Participants were divided into groups based on serum 25-hydroxyvitamin D [25(OH) D] level: 20 women with vitamin D deficiency ($<10\text{ng/ml}$) and 20 women with normal levels ($>30\text{ng/ml}$). Inclusion criteria included maternal age below 35 years, gestational age below 22 weeks, and absence of chronic illnesses, while obese women and those with severe comorbidities were excluded. Both groups had similar baseline characteristics, with no significant differences in maternal age, gestational age, or body mass index (BMI) ($p>0.05$). Obstetric outcomes were assessed and the data was analysed in MS Excel using Chi-square and T-tests, with statistical significance set at $p<0.05$.

Results: The incidence of preeclampsia was significantly higher in the vitamin D deficient group compared to the normal group (25% vs 10%, $p=0.05$). Preterm birth occurred more frequently in the vitamin D-deficient pregnancies (30% vs 10%, $p=0.04$). Low birth weight was significantly associated with the deficient group (40% vs 15%, $p=0.03$) and the mean birth weight was significantly lower ($2600\pm 300\text{g}$ vs $3100\pm 250\text{g}$, $p=0.02$) in neonates born to vitamin D-deficient mothers.

Conclusions: This study suggests that maternal vitamin D deficiency is significantly associated with adverse perinatal outcomes, including preeclampsia, preterm birth, and low birth weight. Given the associated risks, routine vitamin D screening during pregnancy should be considered an essential component of prenatal care. Early identification and timely supplementation of vitamin D-deficient pregnant women could help reduce pregnancy complications and improve neonatal health.

BIOLOGICAL RISK FACTORS FOR SPONTANEOUS MISCARRIAGE

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Introduction: Spontaneous non-pregnancy is one of the most urgent problems of obstetrics, as it has not only medical, but also economic and social character. Thanks to the Decrees and Resolutions of the President of our Republic undertaken in recent years to reduce reproductive and perinatal losses, there has been a significant reduction in these indicators. Meanwhile, despite the reduction of perinatal losses, if a certain family cannot realize its reproductive plans due to non-pregnancy, it is obvious that planning and implementation of preventive measures in relation to these conditions should take into account its causative factors.

The aim of the work was to study the causative factors of pregnancy non-pregnancy.

Materials and methods of research. We examined 166 women with early pregnancy failure (I - group) and 100 women who did not experience pregnancy failure (II - control group). To identify the influence of factors on the occurrence of miscarriage, we determined the role and the strength of influence (weight) of each factor and on this basis modeled the degree of risk of spontaneous miscarriage.

Results of the study. The bulk of women in groups I and II were in the most active fertile age (20-29 years) and the age composition of both groups was almost identical, except for 35-40 year olds, the proportion of whom in group I is significantly higher ($11.4\pm 2.4\%$), and the relative risk of miscarriage in them ($RR = 2.85$) is almost 3 times higher than the average.

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